

A scientific education with Nina F. Thornhill

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Abstract: Prof. Nina F. Thornhill has been my PhD supervisor between 2016 and 2019 as part of the PRONTO Innovative Training Network that she also coordinated. I spent very pleasant moments with Nina's former and current PhD students discussing the great influence she had on us. Here is a personal view on the matter.

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1. INTRODUCTION

This is the first time in three years that I am writing something that Nina will not correct, something that will not have Professor Thornhill's quality label on it. This is exciting, and quite liberating. But like in rugby (and many other things that do not involve tackling), creativity is pointless if one does not master the basics. I know what I owe to Professor Thornhill, and I would like to express my gratitude for this.

It would have been a shame to spend years studying physics to end up forgetting about the real world, and Professor Thornhill reminded me that gravity applied to engineering research too. Section 2 is aimed at Nina the physicist. Nina's students in PRONTO unanimously agreed that she was a perfect example of the "Coach" described by Kets de Vries (2013) as a manager who saw leadership as a form of people development. Section 3 is aimed at Nina the teacher. In both roles as PhD supervisor and as coordinator of PRONTO, Professor Thornhill gave us an introduction to the politics of research and development, in the noble sense of making people work together. Section 4 is aimed at Nina the politician. Last but not least, Professor Thornhill has been a prestigious partner to practise multicultural skills. Section 5 is a reference to the small details that made it work.

2. TO THE PHYSICIST

2.1 *Of hammers and nails*

My engineering education has been a succession of problem-solving exercises: build a toolbox of methods and pick the most appropriate to answer a (possibly ill-formulated) question. Therefore, getting back to the tools available has been a compulsive (and comforting) tendency during this PhD. This is the role of supervisors to challenge their students, but I am glad Nina was here to make me think outside the (tool)box when the industry needed solutions.

2.2 *Process data, with words*

Nina brought a major contribution to the field of process data analysis, developing numerous data-driven methods for detection, diagnosis and removal of process and electrical disturbances among other things. However, Nina's students now understand that process data analysis is not limited to data-driven methods. Nina's expectations in terms of descriptive analysis have pushed many of us to reconsider the nature of our contribution to, *in fine*, extend its reach.

3. TO THE TEACHER

3.1 *The voice in our head*

Former students of Nina confessed hearing her voice every time they started writing something down. A voice fed with hundreds of comments on clarity in scientific reasoning or elegance in academic writing. Nina's school of thoughts have produced a series of writers that will spread those stances, sometimes to their own surprise.

3.2 *The reward function*

In some aspects, my PhD with Nina has been a long negotiation, trying to align the research directions with my own research interests. This has not been an easy one, but I think that we are both happy with the outcome. Although Nina has a clear idea on what a PhD should look like, she has been constantly supportive with the personal development of her students, and this needs to be acknowledged.

4. TO THE POLITICIAN

4.1 *Coordination in action*

Nina has lead a series of large projects and I had the chance to see how she coordinated the PRONTO Innovative Training Network. PRONTO involved a wide variety of

organisations and people, with heterogeneous background and diverse personalities. Nina has managed to bring everyone to collaborate and meet the objectives of the project while maintaining a high individual productivity due to the constraints of the PhD. Generally speaking, the experience of PRONTO will provide an excellent reference for industrial research projects that PRONTO graduates may have to manage in the future.

4.2 Disturbance rejection

- Why would you ask *Instagrammers* to write a blog post?
- I don't know, who would do that in 2019?
- How would you get *Instagrammers* to write a blog post?
- Ask Nina!

Nina's track of record in getting things done during PRONTO has impressed everyone, and reminded us the value of diplomacy.

5. COMMUNICATING SCIENCE

5.1 Cracking the code

I cannot help smiling when I think that it took several months for each of Nina's students to get to understand the message behind Nina's comments. How could we know that an *interesting idea* had nothing of interesting until we compared our respective *interesting ideas*? We certainly could have saved time if we did not follow literally those *you-have-to-try* signs, but this is a fair price to pay to get aware of the subtleties of communication.

5.2 I usually don't like to say those things but ...

The PhD is an initiation to a future technical career. From a student's perspective, the PhD is worth what we make out of it during those three to four years. The role of the supervisor is to help us to maximize our potential during this time, but it is up to the supervisor to provide guidance on aspects that will have an effect beyond this point. I am grateful to Nina for those few extra words.

6. CONCLUSION

Someone told me that a conclusion should be in three parts. I'll skip the first two to go directly to the last part. Nina has been a great supervisor, and a very inspiring one. I would have liked to get her opinion on plenty of topics, and I hope we will have opportunities to meet in the future. Thanks again.

REFERENCES

Kets de Vries, M.F.R. (2013). The eight archetypes of leadership. *Harvard Business Review*.